

Astronaut Health: A Comprehensive Review of Space Medicine

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Abstract

Background

Space medicine is a branch of medicine that studies the physical, mental, and emotional health and medical problems of astronauts during space flight. People are always endeavoring to, understand and explore beyond their horizons. The need to explore the world brings with it many challenges, such as traveling to distinct places and colonizing another planet such as Mars. Humans have yet to experience a comparable stay in space and its consequences, so when considering possible future space settlement scenarios, we need to examine the behavioral health issues caused by a lifetime in isolated and confined facilities.

Main Text

This review introduces the field of medicine and explains the various types of environmental challenges associated with clinical and physical effects and decisions regarding drug use. Astronauts have to face many problems like hypoxia, hyperoxia, space motion sickness, decompression illness (ebullism), micrometeorites trauma, bone calcium loss or muscle atrophy, radiation, reflux, and unknown responses to drugs or anesthesia. This too incorporates countermeasures for those challenges like, significance of yoga/meditation, workout, sun blocks, and adequate diet for space travelers aimed at their space mission. In addition, it also introduces future and career in space medicine.

Short conclusion

Space medicine, also known as space flight medicine or aerospace medicine, is a specialized branch of medicine that focuses on the health and well-being of astronauts during space travel. It encompasses the study prevention, and treatment of the unique physiological and psychological challenges experienced by individuals in the space environment.

Key words: Aerospace medicine, Pharmacology, Microgravity, Radiation, Weightlessness.

Background

Space is an extreme environment that is not conducive to human life. In order for humans to live and work effectively in space for extended periods of time, they need technologies that enable survival in extreme conditions (NASA). NASA has been actively collecting medical, human science and environmental data in space for nearly 60 years (1). Space technology or space tech refers to the design, development, manufacturing, and application of engineering principles of devices and systems for space travel and exploration (2). The Space Technology Grand Challenge is an open call for advanced technological solutions that solve critical space-related challenges, dramatically improve existing capabilities, or enable completely new space capabilities (3).

Space medicine, also known as aerospace medicine or astronautical medicine, is a specialized branch of medicine that deals with biological, physical, and psychological health effects and medical problems of flight personnel a reference to spaceflight (4). It can be broadly defined as: "the practice of all aspects of preventive medicine, including screening, health care delivery, and maintaining human performance in the extreme environment of space and maintaining the long-term health of space travelers" (5). This work is carried out mainly by students and academic followers of I.P. Pavlov Scientific School. As you know, cosmonautics has its own theory and practice. The trainees were aviation doctors, whose brilliant representative was V.I. Dazdovsky. In 1947, the Institute of Aviation Medicine of the Ministry of Defense of the Soviet Union was established, and the first group of young specialists began working in this research institute. Many of them are called the founders of Russian space medicine decades later (6). This promoted the establishment of dedicated medical research programs and the development of specialized expertise in space medicine. Baylor College of Medicine's Center for Space Medicine, established in 2008, is the first university to charter space medicine as an academic center or independent department within a university or medical school. Baylor's Center for Space Medicine is a long-standing contributor to the human space program, former leadership of the National Space Biomedical Research Institute (NSBRI), and the number one life sciences research project funded by NASA over the past 20 years. (7)

One of the primary concerns in space medicine is the physiological effects of microgravity on the human body. When exposed to the microgravity environment of space, astronauts experienced various changes, including muscle and bone loss, cardiovascular reconditioning, altered immune function, fluid redistribution, and vision impairments. In addition to physiological challenges, space medicine addresses psychological and behavioral factors that can affect cosmonaut’s well-being. (8) Overall, the field of space medicine plays a critical role in understanding the effects of space travel on the human body and mind, enabling the development of interventions and protocols to ensure the health and well-being of astronauts during their missions beyond Earth.

Main Text:

Physiological and Medical effects of space flight:

Figure 1. How space affects the human body – Infographic. ©Canadian Space Agency", "Credit: Canadian Space Agency", etc.). (9)

During space travel, astronauts face various risks and challenges that can affect their health and well-being. Here are some of the common risks associated with these challenges and their corresponding countermeasures:

S.No.	Space challenges	Associated risk factors	Potential countermeasures
<u>1.</u>	Radiation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Degenerative disease • Radiation sickness • Cancer • Changes in central nervous system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Health monitoring ▪ Medicines ▪ Healthy diet ▪ Radiation shielding ▪ Brachytherapy
<u>2.</u>	Isolation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Behavioral changes • Sleep problems • Fatigue • Decline in mood 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Gardening and journaling ▪ Light technologies ▪ Self- assessments ▪ Virtual reality sessions
<u>3.</u>	Distance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ineffective medications • Food storage challenges • Lack of medical care • Equipment failure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Food and medicine packaging for preservation ▪ Sustainable food systems ▪ Clinical decision support tools

4.	Gravity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced muscle mass • Bone loss • Fluid shifts • Changes in sensorimotor skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Exercise ▪ Medications ▪ Pressure device ▪ Fine motor testing
5.	Environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Altered immune systems • Celestial dust exposure • Temperature changes • Exposure to contaminants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Routine cleaning and air filter ▪ Air quality monitoring ▪ Immunizations ▪ Thermal control systems

Table1. Major Hazards of human spaceflight (NASA) table used after modifications [\(10\)](#)

Increased force during takeoff, and re-entry:

NASA's Human Research Program has identified a decrease in mobility due to flight-related vestibular and sensorimotor changes as a possible risk factor for a human mission to Mars (11). Medical recovery issues relate to: i) spacecraft decompression, ii) collision iii) fire, iv) normal landing injuries (such as loose objects and impacts), and v) after a live landing, they may also involve the risk of drowning in the event of a landing or from the rescue services of the landing season. Immediately after landing, astronauts will experience fatigue, orthostatic intolerance, and neurosensory impairment, as well as sound sensitivity that will affect a person's ability to walk (5).

Space motion Sickness:

Space motion sickness (SMS), possibly caused by entering a weightless environment was experienced by the unexpected and heavy payloads of the astronauts on the Skylab mission (12). Between 60% and 80% of space travelers experience space sickness within the first 2 to 3 days in microgravity (13). SMS is a syndrome consisting of headache, malaise, disorientation, nausea, or vomiting (14). Transcranial fluid transfer causes facial edema of the face and is through to increase intracranial pressure, change the area of vestibular receptors, and cause SMS (13) (15). Conflict theory proposes that when entering a microgravity environment, the loss of inclination-related autolytic signals leads to a conflict between actual and desired signals from the strong body that support spatial orientation. Pre-flight training and in-flight behavior change SMS have been reduced from approximately 70% before (unaffected) to approximately 30% now in the program (16).

Decompression illness

Decompression sickness happens when nitrogen is dissolved in the body under high pressure (NASA). It includes two pathological syndromes: arterial gas embolism and often decompression illness (17). An arterial gas embolism occurs when gas enters the pulmonary vasculature secondary to pulmonary barotraumas (University of California San Diego). DCS is caused by the formation of harmful gases (mostly nitrogen) in human tissues due to rapid decompression, for example when a diver is getting out of the water or an astronaut enters the lower pressure (18).

Micrometeorite injury

Reduce significant spacecraft threats from natural and man-made space debris. Due to the expansion of Micrometeoroid and Orbital Debris (MMOD) in low ground orbit, there is a possibility of MMOD collision or interference with a range of national and international operating assets, as well as a serious threat to space personnel (3). Space air alters the chemical, micro structural and spectral properties of the particular surface of an airless body and is powered by micrometeorite bombardment and solar radiation (19). In an interview, Professor Hugh Lewis, head of the Astronautic Research group at the University of Southampton said that "Every satellite that goes into orbit has the potential of becoming space debris" (20).

Shuttle cabin pollution with toxic chemicals, combustion products

The biggest concern in human spaceflight is the quality of room air. In particular, a crew member may be at risk of uncontrolled exposure to pollutants such as gases (from equipment, electrical equipment, or equipment under test, etc.) malfunction (e.g. Product overheating), fire, etc., or from people themselves (metabolites) (21). NASA developed air quality criteria (SMAC) to define the level of air pollution that must be controlled to protect the health of the crew (22).

Bone calcium loss, muscle atrophy

University of Calgary professor Leigh Gabel said "Microgravity affects a lot of body systems, muscle, and bone being among them". Microgravity-induced osteopenia is a significant and unresolved health risk in space passersby for this reason; many measures are taken today to reduce bone loss. Includes nutritional supplements and physical activity during long-duration space flights and drug intervention (23). Mainly weight-bearing bones (spines, neck, femur, trochanter, and pelvis) lost bones mineral density during space mission in earth orbit: on average, greater than 1% per month for cosmonauts on the Russian Mir space station. (Table 2.) In contrast, there was no significant loss from bones in the upper extremities (14).

Radiation

Radiation is a critical obstacle to manned exploration of Mars based on current spacecraft and radiation shielding capabilities (5). Cosmic radiation consists of three types of radiation: particles caught in the Earth's magnetic field; particles shot into space during solar flares (solar particle events); and galactic cosmic rays, which are high-energy protons and heavy ions from outside our solar system (23). Astronauts are exposed to roughly 40-times more millisieverts of radiation compared to people on Earth. Exposure to space radiation over long-term missions increases astronauts' risk for cancer and cardiovascular diseases, central nervous system (CNS) depression, degenerative tissue effects, or acute radiation syndrome, although effective shielding and radiation shelters aboard spacecraft have helped mitigate those risks (24, 25). GCR ions from outside our solar system are nuclei with enough energy to penetrate any shielding technology used for current purposes, because they can penetrate to much deeper layers of shielding materials than gamma rays and x-rays and produce within tissues long ionization tracks, with strongly clustered damage to central nervous system health (26).

Effects of Radiation on gametes

Effects on male gametes

Spermatogonia are among the most sensitive cells in the body to radiation. Radiation exposures of less than 10 REM (human roentgen equivalent) are known to reduce the level of sperm production (ICRP, 1969), and exposures of less than 50 REM result in temporary infertility. A single exposure is sufficient to cause permanent azoospermia in an individual (14).

Effects on female gametes

The effect of radiation on oocytes is cumulative. A single dose of 300 to 400 rads is sufficient to eliminate oocytes as well as estrogen production from the ovaries. When exposure is fractionated, tolerance to a single dose increases, and primary oocytes show a degree of recovery from cumulative radiation damage (ICRP, 1969). Evaluation of the effects of space travel on the reproductive endocrine system and ovulatory function should continue, and NASA should consider offering preflight gamete cryopreservation for men and women wishing to reproduce after long-duration space missions (14).

Space sickness, reflux

The role of digestive system is an important control point for a scientist to conduct their studies. Simulating microgravity could create some degree of variation in the weight of space in the human body, support his research and provide opportunities for other research (30). Every time people's hearts are exposed to microgravity, their intestinal

barrier weakens affecting their properties. Bacteria such as Salmonella can enter the body through the intestinal wall and causes many diseases like risk for chronic inflammation and infection (31).

Airway/ anesthesia challenges

Airway management in the intensive care unit is more problematic than anesthesia (32). Common challenges in head and neck surgery are shared airways, distorted airway anatomy due to existing pathology; risk of airway obstruction, disconnection, or loss of airway intra-operatively; risk of airway contamination due to bleeding and surgical debris; and the potential for airway compromise after surgery (33). The first difficult airway algorithm was published by the American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) in 1993 and subsequently updated in 2003 and 2013 (34).

Figure 3. An overview of the changes of digestive system affected by microgravity environment. (courtesy of jia-qi yang et.al., (2020) ELSEVIER (30))

Orthostatic intolerance after re-entry

Orthostatic intolerance is one of the medical problems experienced by astronauts returning from space and cardiovascular dysfunction such as hypovolemia and myocardial atrophy has been identified as an important process (35). The reduction in circulatory blood volume can cause orthostatic intolerance- the inability to stand due to lightheadedness or fainting- once astronauts return to earth (25). After a six-month mission on the ISS in 2005, astronaut John Phillips' full vision was compromised by spaceflight-related neuro-ocular syndrome (SANS). SANS was previously known as Visual impairment and intracranial pressure (VIIP) syndrome, but the name has been updated to reflect the uncertainty as to whether increased intracranial pressure is the sole cause of the symptoms. One explanation is that SANS is caused by the displacement of cerebrospinal fluid towards the head and increased intracranial pressure, particularly at the eye level. The pressure causes the back of the eye to flatten, resulting in a change in farsightedness and blurred vision (25), (35).

Figure 4. Spaceflight Associated Neuro-ocular Syndrome (© Canadian Space Agency", "Credit: Canadian Space Agency",etc.)(9)

Unknown response to drugs, anesthesia

When exposed to the environment, all organs of the body and the body undergoes changes that affect pharmacokinetics (PK), thus affecting the safety and use of the drug i.e. radiation exposure can alter the human microbial balance, can increase the risk of DNA damage, and can compromise immune system function (36). Drug safety and efficacy are highly variable among patients. Most patients will experience the desired drug effect, but some may suffer from adverse drug reactions or gain no benefit (37). Exposure to the space environment can lead to physiological adaptations and affect the pharmacokinetics of pharmaceuticals. Changes in the gastrointestinal tract can alter drug bioavailability through changes in the rate of gastric emptying, intestinal transit time, and absorption. Many drugs are excreted by the kidneys. Weightlessness in space has been shown to reduce urine output after oral fluid loading compared with head-down bed rest studies. It is difficult to predict how these changes will affect the PK of individual drugs during spaceflight. For example ; During human spaceflight, acetaminophen (2×325 mg) tended to show a decreased C_{max} on flight day (FD) 0 and an increased C_{max} on FD2 and FD3 while T_{max} tended to increase although there was considerable variability in the data (29), (36). Knowing the factors affecting the use of intrathecal diffusion and treatment with local anesthetics are important guides in choosing the right dose (37).

Table 3. Overview of medical conditions with their countermeasures that have occurred or may occur during space travel.

Space Challenge	Risk Factor	Causes	Affected Site	Countermeasure	References
Microgravity	Musculoskeletal changes, cardiovascular deconditioning, bone loss	Absence of gravity	Muscles, bones, cardiovascular system	Exercise programs, resistance training, artificial gravity	(10), (38), (39), (40), (41), (42), (14)
Radiation	Increased cancer risk, DNA damage, weakened immune system	Exposure to solar and cosmic radiation	Cells throughout the body	Radiation shielding, personal dosimeters, monitoring and limiting exposure	(23), (24), (25), (26), (27), (28), (29), (10), (38)
Space motion sickness	Nausea, vomiting, disorientation	Sensory conflict due to altered gravity and motion	Inner ear, vestibular system	Medications (antiemetics), adaptation exercises, visual fixation	(12), (13), (14), (15), (16), (29)
Sleep disturbances	Insomnia, altered sleep patterns	Disruption of circadian rhythm, noise, stress	Circadian rhythm, sleep cycles	Controlled lighting, sleep aids, relaxation techniques	(10), (46), (47), (48)
Psychological effects	Isolation, stress, depression, anxiety	Confinement, separation from loved ones	Mental health, cognitive function	Psychological support, communication with ground control, recreational activities	(10), (9), (8), (1)
Vision changes	Visual acuity, optic disc swelling, retinal changes	Fluid shifts in microgravity, increased intracranial pressure	Eyes, optic nerve	Vision exercises, protective eyewear, regular eye exams	(35), (25), (9)
Dehydration	Fluid imbalance, reduced urine output	Limited access to fresh water, increased sweating	Kidneys, urinary system	Increased water intake, electrolyte-balanced drinks, hydration monitoring	(10), (30), (5)
Nutritional deficiencies	Malnutrition, bone loss, muscle wasting	Limited food variety, altered metabolism	Digestive system, muscles, bones	Balanced diet, vitamin and mineral supplements, dietary monitoring	(30), (31), (23), (14), (38), (49), (50)
Immune system suppression	Increased infection susceptibility	Stress, altered immune response	Entire body, organs	Enhanced hygiene practices, immune system boosters, regular health checks	(37), (29), (36), (10)
Loss of muscle mass and strength	Muscle atrophy, reduced strength	Lack of resistance and gravity-induced exercise	Muscles throughout the body	Resistance exercises, rehabilitation programs, nutritional support	(5), (10), (40), (14), (9)
Communication delays	Impact on real-time communication and medical consultations	Distance from ground control, limited bandwidth	Communication systems	Predefined medical protocols, telemedicine technology, onboard medical expertise	(37), (29), (36), (10)

Countermeasures for medical challenges of space flight

Importance of Exercise

Exercise keeps your heart healthy, strengthens your muscles and bones, keeps you flexible, and generally makes you feel better (38). Exercise is one of the most widely used and accepted approaches in the US and Russian space programs, allowing humans to stay relatively healthy for more than a year in space (39). Exercise is important for keeping the musculoskeletal system (our muscles and bones) strong and maintaining bones and muscles throughout life. The Station's Advanced Resistance Exerciser (ARED) allows astronauts to perform high-intensity exercises (40). Reduce the cardiopulmonary effects of microgravity, routine aerobic and muscle strength training, bungee cord treadmill exercise, or exposure to low blood pressure (41). Astronauts undergo "resistance" training. They pull the exercise machine in different ways to make it look like they are lifting weights with their hands and feet. They also pedal on a recumbent exercise bicycle and walk and run on a treadmill. Bikes and treadmills can be programmed to resist pedaling and walking, allowing you to get significant movement in microgravity (14).

Hyperbaric chamber therapy

HBOT involves sitting in a hyperbaric chamber – an enclosed space filled with high-pressure oxygen – and breathing. This allows your lungs to take in more oxygen, thereby increasing the oxygen circulating in your bloodstream, causing increased gas dissolution and volume compression, oxygen uptake increases tissue perfusion and causes proliferation leaching other gases such as nitrogen (43),(44). HBOT helps to boost oxygen levels in your blood, which is believed to assist the body in the following ways:

Hyperbaric oxygen therapy can be utilized as a stand-alone treatment or a procedure that can boost the action of medications, such as antibiotics. HBOT can treat a range of conditions, including:

- Crush injuries (tissue deprived of oxygen)
- Carbon monoxide and cyanide poisoning
- Severe anemia and Sudden vision loss (from blockage of blood flow)
- Air or gas embolism
- Wounds and other soft tissue infections, including diabetic foot ulcers and necrosis
- Gas gangrene and Chronic pain
- Delayed radiation injury (damage to tissue exposed to radiation)
- Acute or reduced blood flow to the arteries
- Decompression sickness (usually in divers and miners)
- Burns or compromised skin grafts
- Severe infections that are resistant to antibiotics
- Sudden complete hearing loss (with no identifiable source of injury) (45).

Significance of Yoga and Meditation

It has been suggested that mass yoga practice, through conscious and voluntary controlled breathing, can induce a hypometabolic state and allow participants to more easily tolerate hypoxia (46). The various bodily postures or mudras (called asanas) and yoga breathing exercises (pranayams), along with finger-toe hand gestures (mudras), are claimed to provide stress relief and many other health benefits like slow breathing effects on central and cardiovascular responses to hypoxic challenge (47),(48). Maheshwa-rananda's Modified Bhujangini Pranayama— is increasing the arterial hemoglobin saturation compared to normal resting spontaneous breathing (46).

Food and Nutrition for astronauts

"You can eat anything in moderation. That's all," said Dr. Scott Smith, leader of the Nutritional Biochemistry Laboratory at NASA's Johnson Space Center. Astronauts eat special foods in their spaceship. Favorites include M&Ms, candy, and beef jerky (38). NASA has provided a safe food system for astronauts on 4- to 11-month missions in low-Earth orbit (49). Astronauts also need a balanced diet. Menu selection helps to design a balanced diet with required amounts of vitamins, minerals and calories.

- ✓ Calcium. In space, the lack of gravity signals osteoclasts (the bone resorbing cells) to begin breaking down unwanted bone, leaving osteoblasts (the bone forming cells) unchanged or slow to produce new bone. The end result is a loss of bone mineral. Astronauts lose 1-2% of their bone mass every time they stay in space. Both on Earth and in space, bone loss makes bones weaker and more prone to stress fractures. To combat bone loss, astronauts eat a calcium-rich diet.
- ✓ Vitamin D. Our skin uses a small amount of natural UV light to produce vitamin D. To work outdoors in the space environment, astronauts must wear spacesuits that protect them from ultraviolet radiation. Therefore, astronauts cannot naturally produce vitamin D in sunlight, so they take supplements to solve this problem.
- ✓ Hydration. Our cells need water to make the chemical reactions that sustain us, and the water in our blood helps our circulatory system carry nutrients. Water helps flush out toxins from our body. Everyone—including astronauts—loses water when they sweat, go to the bathroom, and even when they breathe. Astronauts, like children on Earth, need to drink plenty of water to keep their bodies functioning well. Drinking six to eight glasses of water per day is recommended for children and astronauts.
- ✓ Folate. Folic acid is an important vitamin that, among other functions, helps repair cell damage from the sun's high-energy radiation and the pure oxygen that astronauts sometimes breathe during flight (such as spacewalks). Astronauts use a diet rich in folic acid. But there are concerns that vitamins in food may not be stable in irradiated environments (38).

Nutrition is influenced by environmental conditions such as radiation, temperature, and atmospheric pressure, and these are studied (50). The ISS food system undergoes extensive ground processing and testing to minimize the risk of food poisoning. Food grown in spacecraft will have microbiological incorporated testing and cleaning requirements, as well as waste streams into residential air, water, and waste systems (49).

Use sun block

Current strategies to reduce health risks from cosmic radiation exposure include the introduction of shielding, radiation monitoring, and specific operating procedures (10). However, some high-energy radiation can still pass through the shields. Astronauts receive 10 times more radiation than Earth. Such extreme exposure can damage the immune system and make astronauts susceptible to infections during their stay in space. Long-term exposure can damage cells and DNA, causing cataracts and cancer. Astronauts use devices called dosimeters to monitor the amount of radiation received by each person. Once you reach a certain level, you can no longer stay active in space. NASA and other space agencies are investigating the effects of radiation and testing various materials that could be used in suits and spacecraft to protect space travelers from radiation(38).

Medicine

Drug use by astronauts has historically been poorly documented but recent estimates from the ISS suggest that each crew member has four drugs per week. As our knowledge of genetics, Epigenetics, and proteomics has improved, the concept of personalized medicine has taken on a more prominent role in research and clinical practice. Currently, personal medicine for astronauts is limited. With the advent of long-duration missions beyond low-Earth orbit, space agencies must adopt a personalized strategy for each astronaut, starting with individual countermeasures to minimize harmful physiological changes and finding targeted treatments (29). The use of personalized medical approaches for astronauts is needed not only to prevent and minimize spaceflight injury, but also to ensure effective diagnosis and treatment of acute medical problems during missions. Pharmacogenetics is the study of genetic variability and its influence on drug response as part of the personalized medicine approach. Variations in drug metabolizing enzymes, transporters, receptors, and ion channels can alter drug efficacy and risk of adverse reactions. The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) publishes a list of Pharmacogenetics associations with gene-drug interactions and therapeutic recommendations where these exist ([US-Food-Drug-Administration 2021](#)). Inadequate drug exposure causes a risk for no response or toxicity depending on the therapeutic range of the drug (29).

Example of drug use in space: Modafinil is a drug that is prescribed for narcolepsy and other disorders that involve excessive daytime exhaustion. It has been approved in various military situations and for astronauts thanks to its ability to stave off fatigue.

Career in Space Medicine

Aviation and Space Medicine (ASM) is the latest specialty to be recognized by the Royal College of Physicians and the General Medical Council in the UK (1). The Department of Aerospace Medicine is responsible for the organization, planning, and development of headquarters oversight for all activities supporting space medicine, from research requirements to deliverables, including ground-based analogs for space missions, development of vehicles for human and animal access to space, International Space Station activities, planning for future space missions, and supporting the implementation of health and medical technical authorities (51). Space medicine is a rapidly evolving field that continues to advance our understanding of the human body's response to space travel. The research and knowledge gained from this discipline not only benefit astronauts but also contribute to advancements in healthcare on

Earth, particularly in areas such as musculoskeletal disorders, cardiovascular health, and psychological well-being.

Figure 7. Scheme describing the dependence of biological and clinical profiling with environmental cues and length of mission to accomplish personalized approaches for astronauts highlighting how omics tools can be used to move from correlations to causation. Image used after modification (courtesy of lorie et.al., (2021) *frontiers in bioengineering and biotechnology* (29)

The field of space medicine is very vast, with many applications in not just space agencies but consecutively many other agencies. And due to that, there are dozens of sectors proving jobs in prospects of space medicine courses. The list of careers in various employment areas after completion of space medicine degree consists of

- Military and Civilian Aviation
- Radiation health
- Flight Medicine
- Flight Familiarization
- Hypobaric and Hyperbaric Therapy
- Space medicine: Basic Flight Surgeon Training
- Airline Medical clinic
- Aerospace Manufacturing
- Elective subjects such as travel medicine, administration (52)
- Food Technology
- Space physician
- Aerospace psychologist

Figure 8. Career in space medicine and health

Translational medicine

Translational methodologies are currently applied to spaceflight-related dysregulations in the areas of: (1) cardiovascular fluid shifts, intracranial hypertension and neuro-ocular impairment, (2) immune insufficiency and suppression/viral re-expression, (3) bone loss and fragility (osteopenia/osteoporosis) and muscle wasting, and finally (4) radiation sensitivity and advanced ageing (53). The Translational Research Institute for Space Health (TRISH) is a pure virtual laboratory authorized by NASA's Human Research Program to solve the challenges of human deep space exploration. TRISH continuously pursues and funds new research to provide high-impact science and technology solutions that promote cosmic health and help humanity wherever they explore space and Earth (54).

Achievements in linking individuals' genetics to their disease predisposition and response to treatment are expected to lead to cost-efficient approaches to therapeutic intervention. Following such a patient-specific road map is known as "personalized medicine". Personalized space biomedical research can be a new gateway to understand the multidimensional reality that our bodies are exposed to. Personalized medicine should be incorporated into space medicine to take into account these individual differences. With new technologies, such as individualized *in vitro* modeling, 3D-tissue printing and high throughput sequencing, it is possible to start gathering large amounts of data enabling personalized predictions of risk and individualized countermeasures (29).

Astrobiotechnology

As far as in-space research is concerned, modern biotechnology is able to deliver instrument miniaturization and real-time data analysis, two aspects that are crucial in space as space and weight are limited and spacecraft re-entry to Earth is detrimental for biological-sample integrity. Space biotechnology is a field aimed at applying tools of modern biology to advance space exploration. Pharmaceutical and biotechnology companies are using the US ISS National Laboratory to conduct experiments regarding protein crystallization to develop immunotherapy drugs and to test new

technologies for assessing cellular function to improve evaluation of drug effectiveness and safety. (US ISS National Laboratory, 2019) (53).

Conclusion

The primary goals of space medicine are to ensure the safety, performance, and overall health of astronauts before, during, and after space mission. This field draws upon various medical disciplines, including physiology, cardiology, pulmonology, immunology, neurology, and psychology, to address the specific needs and risks associated with space travel. Space medicine presents unique challenges that require innovative solutions to ensure the health and safety of astronauts during long-duration space missions. With the development of new technologies and approaches such as artificial gravity, wearable technology, advanced imaging and diagnostics, robotics and telemedicine, gene editing and gene therapy, bioregenerative life support systems, and personalized medicine, biomedical engineering offers promising prospects for the future.

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